

ISic3323

I.Sicily inscription 3323

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble (?)

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis of San Placido

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR033622

1. [---]io Innocenti
2. [---]V [---]
3. [---]nis hu [---] obito ex
4. [testamento eius os]sa h [eic hic in cella absi] data sunt
5. E[---]L [---] eor (um) statua e
6. [et statua seden]s eius permissum est
7. [---] mat (er) s (ua) p (ecunia) .

Edition: PHI313633

1. [— — — — — — — —]io [I]nnocenti
2. [— — — — — — — — —].V [— — — — — — — —]
3. [— — —]. . [—]. N I, A [—]NIS □ HV[— — —] Obito □ ex
4. [(?)testamento eius os]sa h[eic in cella absi]data □ sunt □
5. E [— — — — — — — — — —] L, I eor (um) statuae
6. . [— — — et statua seden]s □ eius permissum est
7. [— — — — — — — — — —].IAMCAS mat (er) □ s (ua) p (ecunia) .
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284780

EDR 033622

PHI 313633

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At v
Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte
avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 144-145 fig.18

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